

HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01
European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE
101093261

D1.5

Initial Assessment of Developments and Revision of the Scientific Challenges - Controlling Plasma-Material Interfaces with BIT

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

Date of preparation (latest version): 31/12/2023
Copyright© 2023 – 2027 The Plasma-PEPSC Consortium

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable Number	D1.5
Deliverable Name	Initial Assessment of Developments and Revision of the Scientific Challenges - Controlling Plasma-Material Interfaces with BIT
Due Date	31/12/2023
Deliverable lead	UL
Authors	Stefan Costea (UL), Leon Kos (UL), and Jeremy Williams (KTH)
Responsible Author	Stefan Costea (UL) E-mail: stefan.costea@lecad.fs.uni-lj.si
Keywords	Heat Load, Collisions, Cross-Sections, EEDF, MPI, OpenMP, OpenACC, Hybrid Programming, Heterogeneous Computing Systems, Parallel I/O, In-Situ Data Visualization and GPU Offloading
WP/Task	WP1/Task D1.5
Nature	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Final Version Date	31/12/2023
Reviewed by	Pratibha Raghupat Hegde (KTH), Jennifer Faj (KTH), Federica Bragone (KTH), Aleš Podolník (IPP CAS), Gabin Schieffer (KTH) & David Tskhakaya (IPP CAS)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Partner	Date	Comment	Version
UL	10/10/2023	First draft	0.1
UL	12/12/2023	Final draft	0.2
KTH	12/12/2023	Final draft updated for internal review	0.3
UL	18/12/2023	Revised draft after internal review	0.4
KTH	18/12/2023	Final cleanup for submission	1.0

Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we provide an overview of the current status of the BIT1 code and an update on the summary of developments, focusing on both code-related advancements and the underlying physics. These developments lay the foundation for hybrid and exascale computing with BIT1.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Revision of the Scientific Challenge	6
3	Summary of Developments	7
3.1	Physics Development	7
3.2	Hybrid BIT1	8
3.2.1	Porting BIT1 to Multi-core CPUs	9
3.2.2	Porting BIT1 to GPUs	10
3.3	Software Release	15
3.4	Parallel I/O and In-Situ Data Visualization	15
4	Revision of Gap Analysis	16
5	Revision of Roadmap	16
6	Conclusion	17

1 Introduction

BIT1 is a 1D3V (1D in usual space and 3D in velocity space) electrostatic Particle-In-Cell (PIC) Monte Carlo (MC) code. It is optimized for the 1D modelling of the tokamak edge plasma, more specifically the so-called Scrape-off Layer (SOL). BIT1 simulates plasma, neutral and impurity particle transport inside the SOL including their nonlinear interaction, as well plasma-surface interaction processes [1].

The simulation geometry corresponds to the magnetic flux tube limited by the so-called inner and outer divertor plates. The divertors, representing heat resistant plates, are designed to withstand strong heat and particles fluxes coming from the core plasma. Hot plasma (e, D⁺), impurity (e.g. C^{+m}, W⁺ⁿ) and heat source correspond to the particle and heat transport across the separatrix.

After the injection, plasma and impurity particles propagate along the magnetic field towards the divertor. The particles absorbed at the divertor plates can cause injection of secondary particles (secondary electrons, D, C and W atoms). These atoms interact with the plasma in a nonlinear way. Atoms reaching the radial boundaries of the system (i.e. the separatrix and the outer wall) are removed from the system. Impurity ions, C^{+m}, W⁺ⁿ, are also removed from the simulation with the probability corresponding to the anomalous cross-field diffusion coefficient and cross-field gradient length, e.g. ~ 1 cm. The strength of the particle and heat sources and the temperature of the incoming particles are adjusted to match the experimentally observed plasma density and electron temperature in the upstream SOL [2].

2 Revision of the Scientific Challenge

Usually it is assumed that the parallel transport is the most simple and well studied type of plasma transport. In the scrape-off layer (SOL) this is not the case: low collisionality of plasma, different inelastic and short time scale processes, and geometrical effects can cause deviation of parallel transport from the classical one. As a result, the classical transport model can significantly over (under) estimate particle and energy fluxes to the divertor targets. For present-day tokamaks these uncertainties are not essential, but for ITER, where transient heat loads on divertor targets represent one of the greatest threats to target lifetime, they can lead to serious unwanted consequences. Hence, development of realistic kinetic models of the parallel transport in the SOL is of top importance [3].

A number of innovative techniques have been implemented in BIT1, such as the optimized memory management [4] and the nonlinear multi-step multi-particle null-collision method [5, 6].

BIT1 enables to simulate and predict plasma and heat loads to the divertor plates during the steady state and transient events in today's and future magnetic confinement fusion devices [1, 7, 8, 9]. One of the recent results concerns simulation of the SOL of the future generation tokamak ITER [10].

Different atomic physics models have been considered by including 10^2 , 10^4 and 10^6 atomic processes. Simulations indicate that the latter is essential for proper calculation of the electron energy distribution functions: the first two models predict hot electron tails of the energy distribution function, while the last shows no such tail. These hot electron fractions lead to the unacceptably large divertor electron heat loads ~ 16 MW/m², while

the last model shows only 1 MW/m² [11]. Thus, it has been shown that, in the end, kinetic effects do not significantly modify particle and heat divertor loads in ITER [6]. Such simulations require 50 and more million core-hours and represent extremely challenging tasks with a duration of multiple months.

Due to this long waiting period, obtained profiling results in D1.1 were investigated and utilized for Exascale preparation. In this case, the estimate of the Figure of Merit (FOM) for the exascale BIT1 has not changed.

The Figure of Merit was given as:

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{H \cdot t_0}{H_0 \cdot \text{One-week-in-hours}} \approx 9.0 \times 10^4 \text{ cores,}$$

where $H = 5 \times 10^{17}$ and $H_0 = 2.6 \times 10^{16}$ particle time steps are the sizes of the exascale and the original simulation, respectively, and $t_0 = 7 \times 10^6$ core hours is the clock time for the original simulation.

Additionally, in deliverable D1.1, Figure 1 was reported and showed where further BIT1 optimizations should be carried out to maximize the performance gain.

For Exascale platforms, we will need to apply these required improvements to enable such ITER simulations and modelling within 1-2 weeks.

Figure 1: Percentage breakdown of the BIT1 functions where most of the execution time is spent for the *ionization* and *emphsheath* case, respectively.

3 Summary of Developments

3.1 Physics Development

BIT1 has introduced a new model of the collision operator called *dressed cross-section model* (DCSM) that enables the implementation of a large number of atomic transitions (10^6 and more) in its simulations [6].

The DCSM consists of two steps: calculation of averaged cross-sections for excitation collisions from the ground state and introduction of effective cross-sections based on Collisional-Radiative Model (CRM) rate coefficients.

The effective collision cross-sections derived from the DCSM show expected asymptotic behaviour: (i) For low plasma density, they reduce to the conventional cross-sections for single-step transitions from the ground state; (ii) the Maxwell-averaged rate coefficients are equal to the corresponding rate coefficients obtained from the CRM.

In order to test DCSM for realistic applications and study effects of multi-step atomic transitions in tokamak plasma edge, a set of BIT1 SOL modelling have been performed for JET and ITER relevant plasma conditions.

The simulations did not show any significant influence of multi-step transition processes in a JET relevant relatively hot divertor plasma. Contrary to this, the electron heat loads to the ITER divertor plates were strongly affected by the multi-step ionization and recombination processes in the divertor plasma and have to be accounted for in future simulations [6].

3.2 Hybrid BIT1

The current implementation of BIT1 relies exclusively on MPI and lacks support for hybrid, shared memory parallel computing capabilities and GPU porting, such as hybrid **MPI+OpenMP** and hybrid **MPI+OpenACC** for multi-core CPUs, and GPU offloading with **OpenMP (OMP target)** and acceleration with **OpenACC (ACC Parallel)**, respectively.

For BIT1, based on the findings in [12] and a scientific article by Jeremy J. Williams et al., currently under review for porting BIT1 to optimized multi-core CPU and GPU systems with OpenACC and OpenMP, a detailed investigation of the BIT1 code structure is required. Also, due to the particle arrangement complexity of the `arrj` function, it was suggested to begin initial work on the mover function, particle pusher, in BIT1.

In this deliverable, our aim is to report on the enhancement of BIT1's performance with a primary focus on optimizing the particle mover function, one of the most computationally intensive parts of the code in Figure 1.

To achieve this, OpenMP and OpenACC for multi-core CPUs and GPUs have been leveraged, enabling researchers to fully exploit modern hardware for plasma simulations. This optimization effort is set to significantly improve BIT1's computational efficiency for large-scale plasma simulations capable of exploiting current supercomputer infrastructure.

BIT1 was executed on the following two systems:

- *NJ*, an HPC system, is equipped with an AMD EPYC 7302P 16-Core processor, providing a total of 32 CPU cores. Its architecture is based on the x86.64 platform, and it operates all CPUs with 2 threads per core and 16 cores per socket. The **CPUs** operates at a base clock of 3.0 GHz and offers various CPU-related capabilities. *NJ* also hosts two NVIDIA A100 **GPUs**, each with 40 GB of HBM2e memory, 6912 Shading Units (Stream Processors), 432 Tensor Cores, and 108 SM (Streaming Multiprocessors) Count.
- *Dardel*, an HPE Cray EX supercomputer, features a robust **CPU** partition with 1,270 compute nodes. Each used node is equipped with 256GB of DRAM and two

AMD EPYC™ Zen2 2.25 GHz 64-core processors, resulting in a total of 128 cores per node. In addition to the CPU partition, *Dardel* also includes a GPU partition system consisting of 56 GPU nodes. Each GPU node is equipped with 512 GB of HBM2e memory, one specialized 64-core AMD EPYC™ 7453 processor, and four AMD Instinct™ MI250X GPUs with 220 compute units, 14,080 stream processors, and peak double-precision matrix (FP64) performance of up to 95.7 TFLOPs.

3.2.1 Porting BIT1 to Multi-core CPUs

BIT1 employs domain decomposition for parallelization, utilizing MPI for efficient parallel communication and has been coded to execute with a minimum of two MPI ranks for boundary domain requirements [12]. For BIT1 simulations, MPI point-to-point communication is essential for managing information exchange at the domain boundaries, crucial for tasks like the smoother, Poisson solver, and handling particles exiting the computational domain.

In plasma simulations, there might be some region of space where plasma particles concentrate, leading to situations where a certain number of cells has many particles while others have few. This results in work imbalance in the particle mover [12]. This led to the investigation of porting of the particle mover stage in BIT1 using OpenMP and OpenACC for multi-core CPUs.

Focusing on intra-node testing, an in-depth investigation into how BIT1 performs in terms of "execution time" has been conducted, to explore the advantages of utilizing hybrid approaches on the two HPC systems. The aim was to determine if using both MPI and OpenMP/OpenACC, instead of just MPI, would make a significant difference.

Figure 2: Hybrid BIT1 total simulation vs optimized mover function using 2 and 16 ranks per node for 1000 times steps on NJ .

Figure 2 shows executions of hybrid BIT1 total execution vs. optimized mover function using 2 and 16 ranks per node for 1000 times steps on NJ . For both 2 ranks and

16 ranks, our hybrid **MPI+OpenMP** version of BIT1 shows a reduction in both total simulation time and mover function time. This suggests that parallelizing BIT1 with OpenMP threads improves performance by enabling multiple threads to work on the problem concurrently. Similar to OpenMP, our hybrid **MPI+OpenACC** version for multi-cores also results in a reduction in both total simulation time and mover function time. This demonstrates that BIT1 benefits when used with multi-core CPUs, due to better utilization of CPU cores through parallelization.

Looking at the scalability of hybrid BIT1 on CPUs and Figure 2, it is easy to see that with an increase in MPI ranks from 2 to 16, there is a significant improvement in performance for both total simulation and optimized mover function execution times. This shows that our hybrid BIT1 scales well. However, to confirm these findings, our second system, *Dardel*, was used for further investigation with a focus on the optimized mover function using OpenMP (since OpenACC was not used).

On *Dardel*, as seen in Figure 3, the execution time significantly decreases as the number of MPI ranks and OpenMP threads increases, showcasing the potential for efficient parallel executions. For instance, with 128 MPI ranks versus 8 MPI ranks with 16 OpenMP threads, the execution time reduces to 10.55 seconds, a notable improvement from the original 12.72 seconds.

Figure 3: Optimized mover function - scaling up to 128 MPI ranks for 1000 times steps on *Dardel*

3.2.2 Porting BIT1 to GPUs

The challenge of boosting the performance of the particle mover function in BIT1 by tapping into the computational power of GPUs has been systematically addressed. This

part of the deliverable focuses on improving the particle mover function’s “execution time” by offloading it to the GPU using OpenACC and OpenMP. In doing this, we are one step closer for BIT1 being ready for Exascale platforms.

To achieve this target, two main strategies provided by OpenACC and OpenMP were investigated: the explicit approach, where data regions for GPU offloading are clearly defined using directives, and the unified memory method, which simplifies memory management by sharing a common space between the CPU and GPU.

BIT1 OpenACC GPU Explicit:

Initial work began by using OpenACC’s explicit approach on the GPUs on *NJ* for up to 10 time steps for better visualization of profiling results, particularly focusing on the particle mover function. The profiling results, using NVIDIA Nsight Systems, reveal crucial insights. In Table 1, the most time-consuming operation is the asynchronous data transfer from device to host, accounting for 45.5% of the total execution time, emphasizing its significance in the overall computation.

Table 1: OpenACC Explicit: CUDA API statistics

Time(%)	Total Time (ns)	Num Calls	Minimum (ns)	Maximum (ns)	Average (ns)	StdDev (ns)	Name
45.5	2.03e+9	150000	1.14e+4	1.04e+6	1.35e+4	3.73e+3	cuMemcpyDtoHAsync.v2
31.6	1.41e+9	180007	3.07e+3	2.56e+6	7.83e+3	8.36e+4	cuMemcpyHtoDAsync.v2
19.8	8.82e+8	180069	3.19e+3	1.32e+6	4.90e+3	3.02e+4	cuLaunchKernel
2.9	1.29e+8	45021	1.42e+3	5.29e+5	2.86e+3	7.69e+3	cuMemAlloc.v2
0.2	7.21e+6	80	1.74e+3	1.05e+6	9.02e+4	1.44e+5	cuStreamSynchronize
0.0	6.41e+5	1	6.42e+5	6.42e+5	6.42e+5	0.00e+0	cuMemAllocHost.v2
0.0	1.28e+5	2	5.20e+4	7.57e+4	6.39e+4	1.67e+4	cuModuleLoadDataEx
0.0	4.03e+3	1	4.03e+3	4.03e+3	4.03e+3	0.00e+0	cuInit

Further analysis of the CUDA kernel statistics, in Table 2, shows that the primary kernel responsible for the particle mover function consumes 99.7% of the GPU execution time, emphasizing its significance in the overall computation.

Table 2: OpenACC Explicit: CUDA kernel statistics

Time(%)	Total Time (ns)	Instances	Minimum (ns)	Maximum (ns)	Average (ns)	StdDev (ns)	Name
99.7	5.86e+8	180039	2.98e+3	1.25e+5	3.26e+3	4.32e+2	--pgi.uacc.cuda_fill_A2_gpu
0.2	1.06e+6	20	5.22e+4	5.51e+4	5.29e+4	5.85e+2	move0_152_gpu
0.1	5.25e+5	10	5.17e+4	5.32e+4	5.25e+4	4.95e+2	move0_181_gpu

In terms of data movement (Figure 4), the memory operation statistics shed light on the substantial time spent on `memcpy` operations. Specifically, 80% of the GPU time is allocated to copying data from host to device, emphasizing the importance of efficient data transfer strategies.

These findings emphasize the importance of optimizing data movement and kernel execution in the particle mover function. Strategies such as overlapping computation and communication, along with exploring ways to minimize data transfer size, can be instrumental. Additionally, considering the high memory bandwidth of the NVIDIA A100 GPUs on *NJ*, enhancing the efficiency of memory operations becomes pivotal for achieving optimal performance.

Figure 4: NVIDIA Nsight Systems OpenACC Explicit View - GPU porting of BIT1 mover function with 1 time-step on NJ .

BIT1 OpenACC GPU Unified Memory:

Next, the particle mover function has been initially investigated on NJ using OpenACC Unified Memory. The profiling results revealed critical insights into the dynamics of memory management and kernel execution.

Table 3 shows that the primary mover kernel $move0_{152_gpu}$ dominated GPU execution time, accounting for 66.7% with a total execution time of 1.623457 seconds. Similarly the second kernel $move0_{181_gpu}$ contributed 33.3% with an average execution time of 0.8106292 seconds, highlighting the significance of these kernels in the overall computation.

Table 3: OpenACC Unified Memory: CUDA kernel statistics

Time(%)	Total Time (ns)	Instances	Minimum (ns)	Maximum (ns)	Average (ns)	StdDev (ns)	Name
66.7	1.62e+9	20	7.02e+7	8.55e+7	8.12e+7	5.48e+6	$move0_{152_gpu}$
33.3	8.11e+8	10	7.00e+7	8.51e+7	8.11e+7	5.57e+6	$move0_{181_gpu}$

However in Table 4, a notable observation lies in the staggering 98.8% of total time of 2.59 seconds spent on synchronization. The most probable cause for this can be attributed to the time spent waiting for memory transfers to finish, indicating that data transfers dominate execution time. This is to be expected to a degree, since for this initial investigation the focus has been on the particle mover kernel in the code. This results in a relatively large amount of data needing to be transferred between the host and GPU in between calls to the particle mover, but this issue may be alleviated once a substantial portion of the code has been ported to GPU, allowing data to remain on the GPU for longer.

In terms of hybrid BIT1 data movement and the use of a unified memory strategy, the runtime handles the data transfer between the host and the device. One key advantage, aside from programmer convenience, is the opportunity for the runtime to automatically detect instances of overlapping computation and communication.

Figure 5 displays NVIDIA Nsight Systems' view of such overlapping, revealing that the unified memory version exhibited faster overall runtime than explicit copies. This indicates automatic overlapping of computation and communication. However, we observe

Table 4: OpenACC Unified Memory: CUDA API statistics

Time(%)	Total Time (ns)	Num Calls	Minimum (ns)	Maximum (ns)	Average (ns)	StdDev (ns)	Name
98.8	2.59e+9	110	1.15e+3	9.78e+7	2.36e+7	3.86e+7	cuStreamSynchronize
0.8	2.05e+7	2	8.79e+4	2.04e+7	1.02e+7	1.43e+7	cuMemAllocManaged
0.3	6.98e+6	40	6.30e+3	4.60e+5	1.75e+5	1.81e+5	cuMemcpyAsync
0.0	6.61e+5	1	6.61e+5	6.61e+5	6.61e+5	0.00e+0	cuMemAllocHost_v2
0.0	5.32e+5	1200	2.80e+2	1.18e+4	4.43e+2	5.57e+2	cuEventCreate
0.0	4.60e+5	30	7.43e+3	3.18e+4	1.53e+4	9.24e+3	cuLaunchKernel
0.0	3.78e+5	1200	2.20e+2	1.18e+4	3.15e+2	3.96e+2	cuEventDestroy_v2
0.0	2.69e+5	1	2.69e+5	2.69e+5	2.69e+5	0.00e+0	cuMemHostUnregister
0.0	2.02e+5	1	2.02e+5	2.02e+5	2.02e+5	0.00e+0	cuMemHostRegister_v2
0.0	1.42e+5	1	1.42e+5	1.42e+5	1.42e+5	0.00e+0	cuMemAlloc_v2
0.0	7.35e+4	1	7.35e+4	7.35e+4	7.35e+4	0.00e+0	cuModuleLoadDataEx
0.0	1.98e+4	4	1.49e+3	1.49e+4	4.96e+3	6.60e+3	cuStreamCreate
0.0	1.48e+4	4	1.66e+3	8.45e+3	3.71e+3	3.18e+3	cuStreamDestroy_v2
0.0	2.26e+3	1	2.26e+3	2.26e+3	2.26e+3	0.00e+0	cuInit

that BIT1 OpenACC Unified Memory performance is still hindered by substantial data movement between the host and device.

Figure 5: NVIDIA Nsight Systems OpenACC Unified Memory View - GPU porting of BIT1 mover function with 1 time-step on NJ .

BIT1 OpenMP GPU Offloading:

Due to the observed performance gain with hybrid BIT1 on multicore CPU, an investigation was conducted using the OpenMP target construct for further BIT1 GPU offloading. Fig. 6 and 7 provides performance evaluation insights into GPU utilization compared to the CPU-only baseline with 2 MPI and 16 MPI Ranks. Implementations using OpenMP or OpenACC on GPUs exhibit increased execution times, indicating that parallelization strategies may introduce overhead, potentially outweighing the benefits of parallel processing. Among BIT1 GPU implementations, OpenMP Target with 2 GPUs stands out for delivering a substantial reduction in execution time, demonstrating the performance improvement through concurrent GPU utilization, especially when MPI ranks are assigned to dedicated GPUs.

Yet, with promising results, a critical challenge emerges: data transfer constraints during each PIC cycle. Profiling results from Fig. 5 expose the impact of copying substantial data from the CPU to the GPU at each time step, leading to notable performance bottlenecks. Addressing this challenge involves avoiding large data transfers from the CPU to the GPU at each iteration. The exploration of CUDA streams and particle batch processing with OpenMP Target across Multi-GPUs per node emerges as a promising avenue to streamline data transfer and processing, as also observed in [13].

Figure 6: Optimized mover function execution time(s) for 100 time steps using OpenMP and OpenACC Explicit on NVIDIA GPUs.

Figure 7: Optimized mover function execution time(s) for 100 time steps using OpenMP and OpenACC Unified Memory on NVIDIA GPUs.

3.3 Software Release

New I/O focus branch of BIT1 with openPMD has been published on GitLab repository. It will introduce the conversion of `main()` function from C language to C++ language and new C++ functions to write BIT1 plasma profiles to disk with openPMD (HDF5 and ADIOS2 backends).

3.4 Parallel I/O and In-Situ Data Visualization

BIT1 currently employs serial I/O, as outlined by Jeremy J. Williams et al. [12]. However, there exists great potential for the integration of parallel I/O methods in BIT1, alongside opportunities for in-situ data analysis and visualization with the openPMD and its backends, particularly HDF5 and ADIOS2.

Recently, openPMD has been implemented into BIT1. Listing 1 displays that BIT1 profiles of density and temperature of plasma components, electric potential, and electric field can now be saved to disk using parallel write through the openPMD API with HDF5 and ADIOS2 backends.

```

1 // Open File for Writing, .h5 for HDF5 and .bp for ADIOS2
2 series = Series("datafile.bp", Access::CREATE, MPI_COMM_WORLD);
3 series.iterations[0].open();
4
5 Datatype datatype = determineDatatype<float>();
6 Extent global_extent = {1ul*nc*nmpi, 1ul*nsp};
7 Dataset dataset = Dataset(datatype, global_extent);
8 Offset chunk_offset = {1ul*nc*rmpi, 0};
9 Extent chunk_extent = {1ul*nc, 1ul*nsp};
10
11 std::vector<float> n_store;
12
13 long i, isp;
14 float dum=nc2p/area/dx;
15
16 for(i=0; i<nc; i++)
17     for (isp=0; isp<nsp; isp++)
18         n_store.push_back(srho_ave_show[isp][i]*wt[isp]*dum);
19
20 MeshRecordComponent n_mesh =
21     series.iterations[0].meshes["n"][MeshRecordComponent::SCALAR];
22
23 n_mesh.resetDataset(dataset);
24 n_mesh.storeChunk(n_store, chunk_offset, chunk_extent);
25
26 series.flush()
27 series.iterations[0].close();
28 series.close();
29
30 n_store.clear();
31 Tx_store.clear();

```

Listing 1: BIT1 C++ code snippet showing parallel write with openPMD API using ADIOS2 backend.

For the openPMD reading and plotting capabilities in BIT1, the openPMD-viewer has proven effective in handling data stored in HDF5 format. Additionally, a customized Python script, utilizing the `openPMD-api`, has been crafted for the purpose of reading (refer to Listing 2) and plotting data saved in ADIOS2 format. This script provides a flexible solution for visualizing various parameters, such as electron, ion, and neutrals density profiles, as illustrated in Figure 8.

```

1 # Open File for Reading, .h5 for HDF5 and .bp for ADIOS2
2 import numpy as np
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 import openPMD_api as io
5
6 series = io.Series("datafile.bp", io.Access.read_only)
7 it = series.iterations[0]
8 n_rc = it.meshes['n'][io.Mesh_Record_Component.SCALAR]
9 n = n_rc.load_chunk()
10 series.flush()
11 del series
12
13 plt.figure()
14 for i in np.arange(np.shape(n)[1]):
15     plt.plot(n[:,i])
16 plt.ylabel('n [m-3]\n')
17 plt.legend(['electrons', 'ions', 'neutrals'])
18 plt.show()

```

Listing 2: Python code snippet showing serial read with openPMD API for plotting.

Figure 8: BIT1 plot showing e^- , D^+ , D^0 density profiles after 100 time steps with initial plasma using Python, openPMD API and ADIOS2 backend.

4 Revision of Gap Analysis

No revisions have been made compared to the previous report. PIC MC modeling of the ITER SOL remains an exceptionally complex physics task. Therefore, our approach continues to involve the consideration of a reduced-size model but keeping at least the same physics complexity – specifically, the plasma sheath. This alternative maintains a numerical effort similar to scrape-off-layer (SOL) modeling.

5 Revision of Roadmap

The performance analysis of the optimized BIT1 code on the *NJ* and *Dardel* HPC systems demonstrated substantial improvements in execution time, toward BIT1 Exascale readiness. This not only affirms the effectiveness of our optimization strategies but also highlights the potential for further advancements in plasma science and fusion research. The successful integration of MPI, OpenMP, and OpenACC sets the groundwork for ongoing progress in computational plasma science, facilitating more efficient and scalable simulations.

Future research directions for advancing the particle mover and other functions in BIT1 are evident. The exploration of advanced optimization strategies, including fine-

tuning OpenACC directives, loop restructuring, and data layout optimizations, presents promising opportunities for enhancing GPU performance. The objective is to maximize parallelism and minimize overhead for efficient GPU resource utilization. Optimizing OpenACC directives brings the crucial aspect of memory transfers between the CPU and GPU to the forefront.

Furthermore, the introduction of OpenMP target constructs for GPU offloading emerges as a significant avenue for investigation. This addition to BIT1 offers new possibilities for parallelization and performance improvement. Fine-tuning these constructs and exploring their synergies with existing MPI and OpenACC implementations will be crucial for achieving optimal GPU utilization.

Simultaneously, the prospect of developing a multi-GPU version of BIT1 is a compelling direction for future work. Exploring the challenges and opportunities inherent in distributing computational tasks across multiple GPUs has the potential to further accelerate the code. This multi-GPU approach aligns with the trend of leveraging heterogeneous computing resources for high-performance scientific simulations.

In addition, addressing the impact of data movement on overall execution time is a critical focus. Investigating asynchronous transfer strategies, exploring computation-communication overlap, and minimizing data transfer sizes are primary considerations. These efforts are aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of data movement and signify a significant step towards a more streamlined acceleration process. This approach ensures that advancements in both algorithmic optimization and hardware utilization contribute to the continued success of BIT1 for Exascale platforms.

6 Conclusion

A new collision operator, DCSM, has been implemented in BIT1 which incorporates multi-step atomic transitions. It bridges two approaches: present-day coronal approximation-based collision models with the full kinetic models following individual excited states of particles to be developed in the future.

BIT1 is undergoing transformations in order to prepare for hybrid (CPU+GPU) and exascale computing (e.g. parallel I/O). At the same time, more physics is being implemented, namely in the collisional operator, to describe, with unprecedented accuracy, the electron energy distribution function in the proximity of the plasma-facing components of fusion devices.

The integration of a hybrid MPI and OpenMP approach notably elevated on-node performance, highlighting the potential of leveraging multi-core CPUs effectively. The introduction of OpenMP, offered a natural and efficient parallelization strategy, optimizing load balancing and refining overall execution time.

Hybrid approaches combining MPI, OpenMP, and OpenACC for comprehensive parallelization on diverse architectures hold significant promise. Exploring synergies between these paradigms and optimizing their interplay will contribute to achieving optimal performance across a spectrum of HPC systems, ensuring BIT1's versatility and adaptability to various computing environments.

References

- [1] D. Tskhakaya. One-dimensional plasma sheath model in front of the divertor plates. *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, 59(11):114001, sep 2017.
- [2] D. Tskhakaya and M. Groth. 1D kinetic modelling of the JET SOL with tungsten divertor plates. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 438:S522–S525, 2013. Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Plasma-Surface Interactions in Controlled Fusion Devices.
- [3] D. Tskhakaya, R.A. Pitts, W. Fundamenski, T. Eich, S. Kuhn, and JET EFDA Contributors. Kinetic simulations of the parallel transport in the JET scrape-off layer. *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, 390-391:335–338, 2009. Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Plasma-Surface Interactions in Controlled Fusion Device.
- [4] D. Tskhakaya, K. Matyash, R. Schneider, and F. Taccogna. The Particle-In-Cell method. *Contributions to Plasma Physics*, 47(8-9):563–594, 2007.
- [5] D. Tskhakaya, S. Kuhn, Y. Tomita, K. Matyash, R. Schneider, and F. Taccogna. Self-consistent simulations of the plasma-wall transition layer. *Contributions to Plasma Physics*, 48(1-3):121–125, 2008.
- [6] D. Tskhakaya. Implementation of dressed cross-section model into the BIT1 code. *The European Physical Journal D*, 77(7):135, jul 2023.
- [7] R.A. Pitts, P. Andrew, G. Arnoux, T. Eich, W. Fundamenski, A. Huber, C. Silva, D. Tskhakaya, and JET EFDA Contributors. ELM transport in the JET scrape-off layer. *Nuclear Fusion*, 47(11):1437, oct 2007.
- [8] S. Costea, J. Kovačič, D. Tskhakaya, R. Schrittwieser, T. Gyergyek, Tsv. K. Popov, and the EUROfusion MST1 Team. Particle-In-Cell simulations of parallel dynamics of a blob in the scrape-off-layer plasma of a generic medium-size tokamak. *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, 63(5):055016, apr 2021.
- [9] D. Tskhakaya, J. Adamek, M. Dimitrova, K. Hromasova, J. Seidl, M. Sos, and P. Vondracek. Kinetic model of the COMPASS tokamak SOL. *Nuclear Materials and Energy*, 26:100893, 2021.
- [10] International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor. <https://www.iter.org/>.
- [11] D. Tskhakaya. Kinetic and fluid modelling of the SOL. Tutorial invited talk at the 20th European Fusion Theory Conference (EFTC23), 2-5.10.2023, Padova, Italy, 2023.
- [12] J. J. Williams, D. Tskhakaya, S. Costea, I. B. Peng, M. Garcia-Gasulla, and S. Markidis. Leveraging HPC profiling & tracing tools to understand the performance of Particle-in-Cell Monte-Carlo simulations. *Euro-Par 2023: Parallel Processing Workshops: Euro-Par 2023 International Workshops, Limassol, Cyprus, August 28–September 1. Limassol, Cyprus: Springer Nature, arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.16512*, 2023.

- [13] Steven WD Chien, Jonas Nylund, Gabriel Bengtsson, Ivy B Peng, Artur Podobas, and Stefano Markidis. sputnopic: an implicit particle-in-cell code for multi-gpu systems. In *2020 IEEE 32nd International Symposium on Computer Architecture and High Performance Computing (SBAC-PAD)*, pages 149–156. IEEE, 2020.